

FoodSafety4EU

MULTI-STAKEHOLDER PLATFORM
FOR FOOD SAFETY IN EUROPE

D5.3 Methods for public engagement in European Food Safety System (FSS)

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents a methodology for public engagement in the European Food Safety System (FSS) to address the lack of public awareness, limited engagement, and inadequate cross-sectoral cooperation, which pose significant risks to food safety in Europe.

The methodology presented builds upon existing literature and public engagement approaches, offering insights into barriers hindering public engagement and potential solutions to overcome them. By incorporating these insights, individual food actors can enhance their strategies and contribute to a more reliable food safety system.

The methodology developed in this document takes inspiration from the PE2020 project and incorporates three essential elements of public engagement: public communication, public consultation, and public deliberation. **Two workshop formats, namely the public workshop format and the co-creation workshop format, are selected to implement this methodology.**

The co-creation workshop format promotes co-learning and co-deliberation among diverse stakeholders, facilitating the development of effective communication materials and strategies. It emphasizes diverse participation, idea generation, engaged participation, tangible outputs, collaboration, and consensus-building. The co-creation workshop format enables stakeholders to collaborate, exchange knowledge, and collectively develop communication materials, fostering an inclusive and dynamic environment.

Meanwhile, **the public event format serves as a tool to survey and understand societal concerns regarding food safety.** It encourages inclusive participation, engagement of the public, a broad societal perspective, utilization of interactive tools, and informative and actionable outcomes. Public events provide an opportunity to capture comprehensive societal perspectives and inform recommendations and future research initiatives.

The methodology also includes **five additional public engagement tools developed by FoodSafety4EU**, including a Communication Kit, TikTok videos, comics, educational materials, and the FSOLab Methodology Guidebook. These tools offer innovative ways to engage the public and can be easily adopted and reused in various contexts.

Recommendations derived from the workshops emphasize:

- 1. The need for innovative engagement methods to enhance food safety awareness, particularly in areas with limited literacy levels.**
- 2. The importance of fostering cross-collaboration during outbreaks to promote effective communication and coordination.**

Implementing this methodology and leveraging the recommended tools, may help food actors in the European Food Safety System to effectively enhance public engagement, build trust, for creating a more effective and reliable food safety system.

2 Introduction

The lack of public awareness, limited engagement, coupled with inadequate cross-sectoral cooperation pose significant risks to food safety in Europe, thereby impacting the credibility of the EU food safety system. Particularly during times of crisis or scientific uncertainty when information related to food safety is scarce or incomplete, food safety actors face the challenge of gaining public trust. Failing to establish public trust undermines the legitimacy of the EU food safety system.

Preserving the core values of scientific independence, accountability, and transparency becomes crucial when public trust is essential for ensuring food safety. Moreover, food safety is a collective responsibility spanning from the farm to the fork, where each actor plays a vital role within the larger ecosystem. As stated by the FAO, "food safety is everyone's business." This emphasizes the significance of all stakeholders involved in risk assessment, management, and communication processes, as they collectively establish the foundation for a reliable food safety system that benefits all. In the EU, which has adopted the Farm to Fork Strategy, food chain actors play a pivotal role in instilling trust in the food chain. Likewise, consumers and lay individuals, who require accurate and relevant information to make informed decisions at the household level, also bear the responsibility of maintaining equilibrium and minimizing risks. Therefore, engaging and reaching the public is of utmost importance for upholding the legitimacy of the EU food safety system.

Understanding the roles of food actors in the public engagement process and identifying the stages where their contributions are crucial to mitigate the risks of public disinformation and the spread of false information. Such understanding can contribute to the development of a resilient food safety system that can withstand external shocks and risks in the long run.

This document presents the outcomes of a series of workshops and extensive discussions focusing on food safety awareness, public engagement practices, risks, and opportunities. Its objective is to build upon existing literature and public engagement approaches, providing insights into current barriers hindering public engagement and offering potential solutions to overcome them in the future. By incorporating these insights, individual food actors can enhance their strategies and contribute to a more effective and trustworthy food safety system.

2.1 Objectives

In the EU, public engagement is widely acknowledged as a central aspect of responsible research and innovation practices. It is recognized that public engagement can foster a dynamic culture of debate and deliberation on complex research and innovation topics. The PE2020 project highlights several reasons why embracing innovative public engagement (PE) in research and innovation (R&I) activities is essential. These reasons are driven by the need to promote societal acceptance of technological solutions, addressing the limited democracy in R&I decision-making, mobilizing resources effectively, increasing awareness of technoscientific advancements, and avoiding irresponsible use of public resources (Rask et al., 2016, p.17).

The communication approach adopted by FS4EU, as outlined in WP5 "Strategies to improve public awareness of Food Safety and civil society engagement," is inspired by the findings of the PE2020 project. Its aim is to bridge the gap between research and society, empowering actors involved in the food safety system in Europe, such as regulators, risk communicators, and scientists, to engage with the public. This approach facilitates a two-way flow of information and explores innovative ways to inform the public about potential food safety risks. By mobilizing citizens' capacity to engage with emerging challenges, this approach aims to enhance public awareness and involvement.

To develop a methodology that enables European citizens to contribute to the European food safety system in the long term, the recommendations from the PE2020 project's Innovative Public Engagement initiative were applied. The FS4EU methodology considers the roles and responsibilities of various food actors, including policymakers, industry representatives, NGOs, food authorities, researchers, journalists, and others, at different stages of ensuring food safety. By incorporating these recommendations, the approach seeks to foster a collaborative and participatory environment in which stakeholders across the food safety landscape can contribute to shaping effective policies and practices.

2.2 Background

The concept of public engagement, as introduced by Fischhoff B in 1995 and further developed by Rowe and Frewer (2005), has gained international recognition and popularity. It encompasses the involvement of the public in agenda-setting, decision-making, communication, and policymaking processes. In contrast to traditional top-down approaches, public engagement emphasizes the active participation of the public rather than policymaking behind closed doors (Rowe and Frewer, 2005, p. 254).

Rowe and Frewer distinguish public engagement from non-participatory forms of engagement such as public communication and public consultation, which involve a one-way flow of information from the sponsor to the public. Public engagement, on the other hand, enables two-way communication and facilitates public participation. At the EU level, there is a growing shift towards more inclusive and interactive forms of engagement, signalling a transformation in how civil society is involved in research activities. This shift places greater emphasis on engaging citizens and stakeholders in defining research needs, shaping research priorities, and participating in research and innovation implementation.

The PE2020 project has identified five main categories of public engagement: public communication, public activism, public consultation, public deliberation, and public participation. These categories are characterized and differentiated by the flow of information between the sponsor and representatives of the public. The diverse range of interaction possibilities suggests that public engagement is a dynamic and multifaceted concept.

<p>Public communication</p>	<p><i>the aim is to inform and/or educate citizens. The flow of information constitutes one-way communication from sponsors to public representatives, and no specific mechanisms exist to handle public feedback (examples include public hearings, public meetings and awareness raising activities).</i></p>
<p>Public consultation</p>	<p><i>The aim is to inform decision-makers of public opinions on certain topics. These opinions are sought from the sponsors of the PE initiative and no prescribed dialogue is implemented. Thus, in this case, the one-way communication is conveyed from citizens to sponsors (examples include citizens' panels, planning for real and focus groups).</i></p>
<p>Public deliberation</p>	<p><i>the aim is to facilitate group deliberation on policy issues of where the outcome may have an impact on decision-making. Information is exchanged between sponsors and public representatives and a certain degree of dialogue is facilitated. The flow of</i></p>

	information constitutes two-way communication (examples include ‘mini publics’ such as consensus conferences, citizen juries, deliberative opinion polling).
<p>Public participation</p>	<i>the aim is to assign part or full decision-making power to citizens on policy issues.</i> Information is exchanged between sponsors and public representatives and a certain degree of dialogue is facilitated. The flow of information constitutes two-way communication (examples include co-governance and direct democracy mechanisms such as participatory budgeting, youth councils and binding referendums).
<p>Public activism</p>	<i>the aim is to inform decision-makers and create awareness in order to influence decision-making processes.</i> The information flow is conveyed in one-way communication from citizens to sponsors but not on the initiative of the sponsors as characterises the ‘public consultation’ category. (Examples include demonstrations and protests).

Categories of PE (Source: Deliverable 1.2 of the PE2020 project)

Food safety literature has long been concerned with the theme of public engagement at different points in time amid several issues gaining prominence – namely, a rise in public demand for information and involvement, existing education, and knowledge gaps, need for trust in institutions and public acceptability.

In a recent study titled "The evolution of food safety risk communication: Models and trends in the past and the future" by Kasza et al. (2022), the authors highlight the historical necessity of transitioning from a one-way direct communication approach to integrating public engagement methods among food safety authorities. The authors trace the evolution of food risk communication models and identify triggering moments that have prompted authorities to revise and expand the scope of their risk communication activities at each step of the process. These triggering moments include factors such as rising public demand, limited success of educational initiatives, trust issues, lack of public involvement, and limited effectiveness of communication campaigns in influencing, or changing behaviour.

The study emphasizes that food authorities have increasingly incorporated deliberative and participatory approaches throughout this evolutionary process. They have shifted their focus from minimizing the impact of specific crises to raising general awareness and understanding the psychological aspects of food risk-related situations in everyday life (Kasza et al., 2022, p.5). The shift towards more dynamic approaches, which consider multiple channels and flows of information, aligns with the findings of the PE2020 project. The PE2020 project reported that 36 out of 38 research projects studied had adopted two-way or multiple-way communication approaches (Rask et al., 2016, p.30).

Effective mechanisms for public participation

A public engagement mechanism refers to techniques, processes, or instruments that facilitate the desired interaction between the public and relevant stakeholders. However, many sources point to the dynamic nature of public engagement, which makes determining the appropriate participation mechanism a challenging, particularly when considering measures and robust success criteria, as well as elusive concepts

like public trust that are difficult to quantify. The literature identifies a wide range of mechanisms for public engagement, including specific approaches such as "task forces," "workshops," and "citizen referenda," as well as broader concepts like "public information programs" and "citizen employment" (Rowe and Frewer, 2005).

In 2021, EFSA compiled a list of 50+ online and offline methods conducive to designing participatory processes that engage with third parties in a mutually rewarding way. Aligning with the literature, EFSA emphasizes the importance of having a clear participation objective and defines a method as an activity aimed at engaging an audience to achieve a specific objective.

In the EFSA handbook, each proposed method or mechanism is paired with a predefined purpose, such as generating ideas, learning from and consulting experts and stakeholders, gathering data, informing, learning and sharing lessons within groups, co-designing, and assessing benefits and risks. Similarly, PE2020 has developed its own criteria based on the factors observed in successful public engagement among partners in the 38 research projects studied. Key attributes identified include "political relevance, wide representation, deliberation, democratizing, explorative, and innovative" as procedural virtues, while "empowerment, political influence, enhanced capacities, cross-pollination of institutions, institutional transformation, conceptual creativity, and education" are considered utilitarian goods.

In summary, selecting an appropriate public participation mechanism and assessing its effectiveness can be a challenging task due to the diverse array of techniques, processes, and criteria associated with the dynamic and multifaceted nature of public engagement. The concept of a "participation objective" can be related to the flow of information, such as information exchange, education, or support building, or it can be tied to addressing specific problems, such as lack of confidence, alienation, or inadequate information, further contributing to the complexity of the process (Rowe and Frewer, 2005).

Food safety awareness and public trust in Europe

The Eurobarometer (EB97.2, 2022), a robust tool for studying public perception in Europe with responses from 26,509 individuals across 27 EU Member States, reveals a high level of public awareness regarding food risks. European consumers are well informed about additives such as colours, preservatives, or flavourings used in food and drinks (70%), pesticide residues in food (65%), antibiotic, hormone, or steroid residues in meat (63%), and diseases affecting livestock or humans (60%). However, there are variations in awareness levels, with less knowledge about poisonous moulds in food and feed crops (38%), the use of new biotechnology in food production, such as genome editing (29%), and nanotechnology in food production (25%).

Public trust in authorities and institutions related to food safety also exhibits country-level variation. The 2022 study shows that 8 in 10 respondents have the highest level of trust in scientists for food safety information, followed by consumer organizations. However, trust in national authorities is lower in countries such as Croatia, Slovenia, and Poland compared to other countries.

On the other hand, insights from the EU-funded project SafeConsume¹, which aims to reduce the health burden from foodborne illnesses, reveal some risky behaviours in domestic environments. Limited understanding and prevalence of unsafe practices are identified as the main causal factors. It found that

¹ <https://safeconsume.eu/>

certain groups, such as the elderly, young families with children, pregnant women, and young single men (categorized as "risk takers"), are more prone to specific foodborne disease risks (e.g., Octavian et al., 2022).

Meanwhile, there is an emerging problem in Europe with public confidence being easily manipulated and undermined by the spread of unreliable or unverified information related to food safety. To this end, the EFSA 2021 report highlighted a need for further investigation into disinformation patterns, focusing on socio-cognitive factors and characteristics of specific target groups, as these aspects are not well covered in the existing literature.

All the above emphasizes the discrepancies that may exist between reported levels of knowledge obtained from attitudinal surveys and actual behavioural patterns. Therefore, a deeper understanding of daily routines and the psychological aspects of food risk situations is crucial, supported by dynamic engagement mechanisms.

How effective public engagement can stimulate food safety awareness and public trust

As mentioned earlier, public engagement is an evolving trend that responds to the societal need for greater openness and transparency in science and innovation practices. It necessitates the involvement of citizens and stakeholders in various stages, such as defining research needs, setting priorities, and implementing initiatives. The increasing adoption of deliberative approaches by EU projects, exemplified by PE2020, indicates that this approach facilitates the required public participation for societal acceptance, democratic decision-making in research and innovation, and improved awareness. However, determining the appropriate level and effectiveness of public engagement, along with the suitable format, is complex due to factors like interaction objectives, understanding the problem, context, and success criteria. These factors are challenging to measure, given the dynamic and elusive nature of concepts and the ever-expanding array of engagement mechanisms.

Considering the vulnerabilities surrounding food safety awareness and public trust, the Eurobarometer 2022 study identifies three primary reasons for low citizen engagement in Europe regarding food safety issues. Firstly, citizens tend to take for granted that the food sold is safe. Secondly, there is a discrepancy between perceived knowledge of food risks and actual knowledge. Lastly, the technicality and complexity of presented information pose challenges. Considering the increasing complexity of science in a rapidly changing environment, influenced by multiple drivers like climate change and changing consumer preferences, coupled with the spread of false information from various sources, authorities and other food actors face the formidable task of engaging with the public in innovative and dynamic ways to earn trust and confidence.

The 2021 EFSA engagement handbook, which offers more than 50 methods, tips, and best practices for designing effective participatory processes, serves as a foundation for applying the innovative approaches of the FS4EU project. This project aims to develop a mechanism that addresses the challenges faced by public authorities and other food actors in fostering awareness and trust in a dynamic and ever-changing global environment.

The next section will describe the methodology and approach adopted by the FS4EU project, including the criteria for selecting an appropriate public engagement mechanism and the procedural steps taken to facilitate desired interactions with the public and stakeholders, which helped to inform the public engagement methodology.

3 Method

The overarching methodology involves organizing a series of workshops focused on specific food safety issues in selected geographical areas, referred to as Hubs. These workshops serve as experimental spaces to implement various formats, including public workshops and co-creation workshops.

3.1 The Hub workshops

The goal of the workshops was to enable stakeholders and citizens to actively contribute to the development of communication tools and methodologies that catered to their specific needs in terms of information, engagement mechanisms, and tools. Additionally, the workshops aimed to facilitate the sharing of best practices and ideas on how to sustain ongoing interactions between the public, researchers, and policymakers in the future.

To ensure the desired interaction, the selection of the engagement mechanism was based on our participation criteria, drawing on the PE2020 guidelines and Rowe and Frewer's typology (2005) as a foundation for understanding how to choose a mechanism that would fulfill the participation objectives.

Firstly, it was essential to establish a "two-way" interaction with all interested citizens. The chosen method needed to incorporate a combination of communicative, consultative, and deliberative elements, as supported by existing literature. Furthermore, involving citizens in discussions about their preferred modes of interaction with researchers and policymakers, while encouraging broad stakeholder participation, was crucial to ensure a diverse representation of actors in the process. The EFSA's 2021 guide served as a valuable resource, providing a starting point for identifying potential mechanisms and formats that could be explored and expanded upon, as well as understanding their key features, risks, and benefits.

Drawing inspiration from these considerations, FoodSafety4EU integrated all three essential elements of public engagement in the food safety system: public communication, public consultation, and public deliberation. Two workshop formats, namely the public workshop format and the co-creation workshop format, were selected to implement this methodology. The following sections provide a detailed description of these methodologies, including their advantages, disadvantages, and the rationale behind their selection.

3.1.1 Public workshop format

In this workshop format, the initial stage comprises individual presentations by keynote speakers. These presentations serve as a starting point to introduce and contextualize the problem under consideration, while providing additional insights to the participants regarding public communication. Subsequently, a moderated panel discussion is conducted, led by an expert with experience in social cooperation or a background in Social Science and Humanities. It is important to note that this expert does not necessarily require technical food safety expertise. The panel discussion is accompanied by an online question and answer session, enabling participants to engage in interactive discussions and pose questions. Moreover, participants are encouraged to contribute their own questions, thus facilitating public consultation. To foster a dynamic and interactive atmosphere, digital tools such as Sli.do and Mentimeter can be employed.

The information and inputs gathered during the public workshop are carefully analysed and processed by the organizers, who are the partners of the FoodSafety4EU project in this case. These insights are then utilized to develop new models that support and enhance public engagement in the food safety sector, thereby contributing to ongoing improvements in the field. [Table 1](#) below presents a template used for guiding the definition of the workshop according to the format developed.

Table 1 illustrates a potential strategy for implementing the public workshop format.

5 minutes	Introduction
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A representative from the FoodSafety4EU consortium gives a short introductory presentation, outlining the key objectives and structure of the session, as well as highlighting the relevant themes it will aim to address.
10-20 minutes	Introductory presentations
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thanks to short and condensed presentations, two or more keynote speakers will contextualise the topic of the event, also providing elements of discussion for the following session(s).
At least 1 hour – max 1,5 hour	Interactive panel debate with experts followed by a public discussion
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The goal of this session is to encourage an interactive debate among the panelists on best practices for communication and public engagement, through a moderated round table, integrated by a Q&A session with the audience, which will pave the way for a discussion with the wider public. Experts, coming from different typology of entities (i.e., food safety authorities, academia & research, NGOs & media, etc.) and from different areas of expertise (i.e., regulation, food safety, communication, etc.) are requested to address moderated questions from their perspective (i.e., as a researcher, as a risk manager, etc.). At least 3 rounds of questions are done, asking to panelists to reply using max 2-3 minutes each round. Questions can be: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The same for all panelists, that will reply differently according to their activities and expertise Specific for each panelist, so adding additional elements to the topic discussed. The audience will be invited to engage in an active dialogue via the use of a smartphone/laptop through online tools e.g., Slido/Mentimeter. <p>Moderators: 1 or 2 people with a background on social collaboration or any other SSH one</p> <p>Panel experts: Always include experts representing different sectors and entity typology (max 4-5), for instance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> An expert from academia or research An expert representing the food safety authorities An expert in risk communication, science communication or public engagement A representative of civil society, consumers or citizens
5-10 minutes	Wrap-up and main conclusions
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To ensure a summary of the main insights emerged from the discussion and to explain the follow-up of the workshop

This approach has the following strengths:

- It can bring to the table different actors with different expertise and background, ensuring a wide variety of opinion and easing that the topic is addressed in a systemic way.

- It ensures a constant integration of the public in the discussion, including the possibility to bring their opinions in the discussion with experts.
- It is suitable for workshops with a high attendance, without the risk of losing relevant opinions.
- It enables organisers to make sure that the discussion is guided around the topic (mainly, thanks to the preparation of the questions for panellists and the audience), ensuring that results collected are meaningful.
- It gives organisers the possibility to analyse and elaborate the insights collected, also easing the possibility of potential follow-up of the results obtained.
- It is extremely suitable for the definition of recommendations, possible actions to be further investigated, etc.

However, this approach could also have some shortcomings that should be considered:

- It does not deliver “tangible” output, i.e., the definition of a new way to better communicate the food safety, but it can provide elements for further investigation.
- Insights collected really depends on the variety of the stakeholders attending the workshop, that could bias the conclusions.

3.1.2 Co-creation workshop format

The second proposed format is the co-creation workshop format, which draws inspiration from the recommendations of the PE2020 project. This format recognizes the untapped potential of co-creating knowledge through public engagement. In specific contexts, the co-creation workshop format was offered as a means for citizens and stakeholders to contribute in innovative ways to the generation and output of scientific knowledge within the public engagement process.

Considering the intricate nature of scientific knowledge pertaining to food safety, the co-creation workshop format incorporated a combination of introductory presentations and a panel discussion involving diverse stakeholders (public communication). This segment aimed to address potential knowledge gaps and existing variations in stakeholders' understanding of food safety. Following this initial phase, which aimed to inspire the audience by highlighting challenges and fostering groundbreaking ideas, participants engaged in a co-creation activity. Facilitated by moderators who may or may not possess a technical background, participants worked together in groups to design solutions (public deliberation) for the issues presented during the first part of the event.

Table 2 illustrates a potential strategy for implementing the cocreation workshop format

5 minutes	Introduction
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>A representative from the FoodSafety4EU consortium gives a short introductory presentation, outlining the key objectives and structure of the session, as well as highlighting the relevant themes it will aim to address.</i>
15-20 minutes	Introductory presentations
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Thanks to short and condensed presentations, two or more keynote speakers (with relevant experience of the issue) will contextualize the topic of the event, also providing elements of discussion for the following session(s). They can focus also on a specific case study.</i>
At least 1,5 hour	Co-creation exercise and presentations
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Using the insights from the presentations (and focusing on different perspectives) the participants are involved in the co-creation of a solution (i.e., guidelines, communication activities, recommendations, etc.) to solve the</i>

	<p><i>challenge identified (i.e., how to deal with a food safety crisis spreading and misrepresented in media);</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The participants are organised in small groups (5-10 people) and guided by a facilitator, that helps to animate the discussion and facilitate inclusive dialogue.</i> • <i>Participants define their solution using a template provided by the organisers, that provides the rules to be followed and the main questions to be addressed.</i> • <i>When the time dedicated to the co-creation is over, each group present its solution to the rest of the participants, that can make questions and discuss what proposed.</i>
5-10 minutes	<p>Wrap-up and main conclusions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>To ensure a summary of the main insights emerged from the discussion and to explain the follow-up of the workshop</i>

This approach has the following strengths:

- It can bring to the table different actors with different expertise and background, ensuring a wide variety of opinions: in this case, they are also actively working on finding a new solution, built thanks to the integration of different expertise.
- It can enable the generation of new ideas that could be followed-up after the workshop.
- It is suitable for workshops with a limited number of participants, that are also actively involved.
- It enables organisers to make sure that the workshop has a tangible output, on which they can investigate more or that can be developed further after the event.
- It is extremely suitable when there is a weak collaboration between different stakeholders on a specific topic and/or when the opinions are polarised: indeed, actors are requested to talk each other and find a compromise.

However, this approach could also have some shortcomings that should be considered:

- Results generated really depends on the composition of the working groups, that should be variegated in terms of expertise and actors.
- It requires a certain level of experience in the moderation of the groups to stimulate a fruitful discussion, otherwise there is the risk that results produced are not qualitatively acceptable.

3.1.3 Application in the FoodSafety4EU workshops

The FoodSafety4EU workshops were conducted at EU level as well as in the four predetermined Hubs: Western, Southern, Eastern, and Northern Europe, led by their respective coordinators in Portugal, Italy, Belgium, and Finland. The Hub approach developed by FS4EU recognizes that specific food production chains, market dynamics, and innovation/technologies can vary across geographical regions, thereby influencing public perception.

The Food Safety Hubs serve as decentralized nodes, aiming to bring together local experts for multi-actor discussions. This approach ensures that the developed engagement models are sensitive to the varying levels of public awareness across the EU and the country-specific rates of participatory performance observed in the PE2020 project.

A total of four workshops were organized by the Hub coordinators, acting as the primary means of engaging the public on specific topics relevant to their respective regions in Western, Southern, Eastern, and Northern Europe. Additionally, a workshop at the EU level was organized by EUFIC during EU Green Week, which set

the overall framework and initiated the discussions. This strategic decision allowed for maximum visibility and explored food safety issues at the EU level, involving high-level stakeholders and developed an approach that could be adopted by the Hub leaders.

For the regional workshops, the local Hub coordinator took responsibility for the planning, preparation, and implementation of the workshops in their respective Hubs, including the selection of the moderator. EUFIC provided overall guidance materials and the two methods for designing public interaction in accordance with the PE guidelines. APRE was responsible for designing the promotional strategy. The local coordinator had the flexibility to assess the suitability of the workshop format within the local cultural context, drawing insights from surveys, research literature, and current issues ("hot topics") to determine relevant themes and set participation objectives.

3.2 Selecting a relevant problem

In the EU, the policy agenda, particularly the From Farm to Fork Strategy under the EU Green Deal, places significant importance on transitioning towards more sustainable food systems and healthier diets while ensuring high levels of food safety. This is particularly relevant as novel foods and methods are introduced into the food supply chain, presenting new and difficult-to-assess risks.

The complexity of the environment poses challenges to public awareness regarding food risks. As commented on previously, while the 2022 Eurobarometer suggests high levels of public awareness of food-related risks, insights from behavioral research indicate some nuances. Firstly, the emerging issue of public confidence being easily manipulated by the spread of false information related to food safety further highlights the vulnerabilities of the current EU food safety system to external shocks. Within the PE2020 project, the selection of a societal challenge was identified as the third criterion for innovation in public engagement.

Considering the context described above, **the main societal challenges affecting food safety engagement relates to the complexity of science in a changing global environment**, influenced by factors such as climate change and changing consumer preferences, and how consumers perceive food risks in this context. **The second salient issue relates to public trust in institutions amid a high risk of false information being disseminated from various sources.**

Given the significance of the problems identified in the literature, specifically consumer risk perception and public trust, and considering the EU context, the workshops and models sought to explore these difficulties, which has led to challenges in mobilising citizens and relevant stakeholders to participate in food safety research and policy activities, in various context. The two main overarching themes explored by the workshops related to:

- a. **Overall lack of public engagement related to food safety:**
 - i. **Among citizens**, the 2022 Eurobarometer identifies three main reasons for the current lack of public engagement in food safety issues: 1) citizens assume that the food sold is safe; 2) a discrepancy between perceived knowledge of food risks and actual knowledge; 3) the technicality and complexity of scientific information.
 - ii. **For food actors**, evidence attributes factors such as resource constraints, institutional culture and public/stakeholder attitudes limiting the possibilities of food actors to develop the necessary mechanisms to engage with the public (EFSA 2019), posing significant challenges for building public awareness and trust.

- b. **Lack of dialogue and cooperation between actors when conducting science and communicating externally:** Similarly, research highlights the need for dialogue and cooperation between authorities and actors at the national and EU levels, which can inform more harmonized communication. Lack of resources and coordination mechanisms are among the hindering factors (EFSA 2021), further contributing to the possibility of disinformation and the spread of false information, which in turn limits awareness and trust.

Based on these considerations, each Hub workshop coordinator had the opportunity to focus on a specific food safety issue or challenge relevant to the context, to facilitate discussions with stakeholders about the themes applicable to the local or regional context. This provided an ideal opportunity to learn about specific challenges, bottlenecks, and barriers to public engagement in practical environments.

Table 3 – overview of the issues selected for the Hub level workshops.

FS4EU Hub – WORKSHOP format	Issue/topic	Justification
ALL THE HUBS EU Green Week (EU/online) <i>Public event</i>	Sustainability challenges related to the Farm to Fork Strategy How can we communicate food safety in the context of sustainable food systems	EU policy agenda is transforming the way we eat and placing importance on the transition towards more sustainable food systems and healthy diets. Novel foods/methods being introduced into the food chain may present new, hard to assess, emerging risks. How can public engagement be sustained on issues driven by uncertainty and complexity?
Northern (Finland/hybrid) <i>Co-creation workshop</i>	Novel proteins and consumer trust	Boosting consumer acceptance towards alternative proteins is of high importance amid the sustainable food systems transformation promoted by EU policy. Although the data collected by the NextGen proteins survey reports consumers overall attitude is positive, their personal interest to use food applications is much lower. A large share of consumers does not yet have an opinion of new protein sources.
Southern (Portugal/online) <i>Public event</i>	Effective communication	Public communication is an important dimension of public engagement (e.g., education, awareness-raising campaigns). But do we really know what effectiveness means in the context of food safety communication and do we have promising measures to assess success?
Western (Belgium) <i>Cocreation workshop</i>	False information case study: salmonella in chocolate	Most food safety topics are already prone to the risk of misinformation, let alone during a food crisis context. What

		can we learn about the specific example of the salmonella and chocolate scandal in Belgium to ensure good public engagement is guaranteed in the future?
Eastern (Romania) <i>Public event</i>	Future of food safety	The future of food safety looks uncertain amid drivers like climate change, consumer preferences and EU policy changing the food system dynamics. This shift may present challenges from a public engagement point-of-view.

4 Analysis

4.1 Food safety challenges

The five workshops covered a diverse range of food safety topics, highlighting the **intricate nature of food safety information and the stakeholders' need for additional knowledge**, particularly regarding novel foods, alternative proteins, chemical risks, food-borne diseases, antimicrobial resistance (AMR), GMOs and new genomic techniques, climate change and its impacts, as well as food handling practices, food waste, and contamination. These topics frequently emerged in the discussions, demonstrating their relevance and importance from a public engagement standpoint.

On a broader level, **public trust was identified as a significant barrier to effective public engagement, along with the complexity of scientific information**. The conversations revolved around the necessity to promote clear, concise (yet not oversimplified), direct, and targeted messages that prioritize the audience's perspective. This approach aims to reach consumers and other non-expert audiences who may find the language and terminology associated with food risk information difficult to understand. The role of beliefs and emotions in communication was also deliberated, and some panelists advocated for a collective agreement on trusted and authoritative sources to address challenges stemming from conflicting views and messages. The workshops, which employed a case study approach, tended to emphasize specific areas more than others.

4.2 Engagement

The panel composition in the five workshops was successfully balanced, ensuring a diverse representation of food actors. The participation statistics indicate that the audience participants were relatively dispersed overall, in line with the aim (see Annex 1).

Regarding the quality of engagement, **the co-creation workshops provided valuable insights into stakeholder dynamics within specific contexts, offering novel perspectives not previously documented in the literature**. A notable example is the Belgian salmonella in chocolate crisis and the response strategies adopted by various actors, as well as the exploration of novel proteins in Finland. The experimental co-creation workshop formats implemented in the Northern and Western Hubs fostered creative thinking and generated innovative ideas, allowing participants to actively shape the problem statement and design solutions for specific scenarios.

The three public workshops, one conducted in-person (Eastern Hub) and two held online (EU Green Week and Southern Hub), facilitated lively debates on various topics through audience Q&A sessions. The online workshops attracted a larger number of participants compared to the in-person event due to their broader accessibility, with attendance ranging from 80 to 120 individuals. However, the participation statistics indicated a broader geographical spread, extending beyond the workshop regions. This naturally shifted the discussions from local or regional issues to broader EU-level concerns. The level of engagement with the audience was more limited and constrained in the online workshops, where participants could only provide input within predefined questions and challenges. Consequently, the debates largely revolved around existing literature and theoretical frameworks. While tools like Slido and Mentimeter facilitated the collection of societal concerns, interactions between speakers and participants remained somewhat superficial. The case study presented by EFSA during the Portugal workshop stood out by providing a comprehensive examination of stakeholder dynamics and regulatory science related to edible insects in the EU context over the past decade. This specific case study enabled participants to delve into stakeholder dynamics, identify challenges and best practices, and engage in more creative thinking.

Workshops centered around case studies that showcased specific issues in unique contexts effectively demonstrated the dynamics among stakeholders under specific conditions, fostering dynamic and creative debates among participants. **The in-depth examination of stakeholder dynamics from firsthand experiences, offered by the case-studies, made the context more tangible and relatable to the audience.** The co-learning approaches employed in these formats facilitated mutual learning, experimentation, and creative thinking, which are crucial for addressing complex topics requiring diverse perspectives (refer to Figure 1 for examples of materials developed).

In terms of participation, while the in-person workshops had a lower overall participant count, **the face-to-face dimension added significant value to the quality of interaction compared to the online workshops, where discussions often remained confined to the level of the speakers or panel experts.** This finding was further supported by feedback from the coordinator of the Belgian workshop, who emphasized the need to leverage the interactive co-creation model for public engagement in food safety, as it offers valuable insights into priority areas and assists policymakers and authorities in shaping their strategies.

Figure 1 Supportive material utilized during the working group sessions in the Finnish workshop. Four personas (Food Safety Authority, NGO, policymaker, and researcher) were used as conversation starters and viewpoints in the co-creation session.

5 Results

5.1 Main barriers to public engagement

The key barriers to engagement identified through the workshop discussions are presented in Table 4, categorized based on the most frequently discussed themes.

Table 4 explaining the main factors constraining public engagement and cross-cooperation related to a thematic area.

Thematic areas	Main factors constraining public engagement	Main factors constraining cross-cooperation
<p>Climate change and sustainability challenges (new risks, pollutants, food waste, new consumption trends, microplastics, GMOs and NGTs)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizens: complexity of information related to unknown risks, education, trust, relatability of abstract concepts • Authorities, and others: scientific uncertainty and communicating the overall complexity in simple but not over-simplified terms • Researchers: harmonizing approaches and messages, integrating transdisciplinary, nonconclusive data. • NGOs: aligning interests between consumers and policy, absence of a 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Societal factors: misinformation and disinformation, timeliness • Scientific level: contradicting evidence, unharmonised methods and approaches, transdisciplinarity, absence of

	common vocabulary e.g. “sustainability”.	agreement about “trusted source”; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Human resources</u>: in-house capacity, funding, lack of education and training on health/food science engagement and communication • <u>Country-specific dynamics</u>: contextual differences among MSs, fragmented interests, accountability mechanisms.
Food outbreaks (food-borne diseases, salmonella etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Citizens</u>: information overload and disinformation, role of emotion, education, trust • <u>Authorities and policymakers</u>: timeliness in response, gathering of information, fighting false information, public trust. • <u>Journalists</u>: access to information from a trusted source, time • <u>Researchers</u>: lower public trust since covid-19 due to citizens’ overexposure to science, cutting through noise. • <u>Industry</u>: lack of in-house communication capacity, timeliness 	
Food handling (hygiene, cross-contamination, preparation)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Citizens</u>: beliefs and myths regarding food labels and food preparation (e.g., temperature for cooking and hygiene practices), education, trust. • <u>Authorities</u>: cutting through the noise 	
Novel foods and new protein sources (insects, allergens, manufacturing process)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Citizens</u>: general attractiveness, palatability and flavour, myths and beliefs, novelty of the products, misinformation • <u>Authorities</u>: lack of social research to inform targeted communication and engagement 	
Governance (role of authorities, traceability, transparency, accountanbilty)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Citizens</u>: complexity of the EU food safety system, misconceptions. 	
Other food safety areas (AMR, chemicals, pesticide residues)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Citizens</u>: education and misconceptions about risks, beliefs, false information, overload. 	

Regarding the barriers, discussions predominantly revolved around the complexities of communicating about unknown and emerging risks in the context of climate change and drivers related to shifting food preferences

and the sustainability transition, where the information is often constantly evolving and thus inconclusive or incomplete. On the level of the consumer, the feature was said to exacerbate the overall complexity of information which made the final message prone to misinformation and misperception. On the level of research, there are some general challenges which have direct repercussions for public engagement - such as the absence of a consensus about the risk assessment methods, definitions for concepts like sustainability lacking, and unharmonized scientific evidence, all requiring more extensive interdisciplinary cooperation. Meanwhile, authorities may face the challenge communicating about uncertainty in simple terms to consumers without oversimplifying the information and making the information relevant and actionable to both consumers and policymakers, who need to take decisions. On the level of NGOs and consumer organisations, difficulties in mediating consumer and policy interests were mentioned by one panel speaker, citing the lack of consensus about key concepts e.g., sustainability as a contributing factor.

On the other hand, a food outbreak was considered highly relevant in the context of covid-19, climate change and the workshop in Belgium which focused on salmonella. It was said that a crisis context may give rise to intense emotion in consumers who are at risk of information overload and prone to oversensationalist rhetoric, particularly when the issue occurs close to home. Amid the problem of low education and fragile trust levels, a food outbreak can easily manipulate beliefs and attitudes and affect the reputation of food actors involved on the crisis-management side of the issue (especially policymakers and food companies). In this context, a lack of in-house capacity and timely information-sharing by food actors can strongly hamper the authority's efforts to communicate in a timely manner and its ability to fight against false information while maintaining public trust levels. Meanwhile, journalists need access to specialists but may face difficulties to get their information from a trusted source, which coupled with a short timeframe can create the perfect conditions for misinformation.

For food handling, old myths and beliefs are said to give rise to bad hygiene practices, wrongly interpreted labels, and in some cases, lead to food contamination and food-borne illnesses due to wrong preparation. Perceptions, especially related to perceived knowledge can create barriers for authorities to cut through the noise and inform adequate behaviour.

On the topic of novel foods and proteins, especially edible insects, while there is overall scientific consensus about the safety aspects is concrete, discussions suggested palatability, flavour, myths and novelty were the main obstacles towards consumer acceptance, since a large share of consumers do not yet have an opinion about new protein source. In this context, authorities that may not have the appropriate capacity for social research may struggle to account for individual attitudinal differences to provide targeted information.

Two other areas were discussed, namely complexities surrounding EU food safety governance and the ill-understood roles and public misconceptions leading to accountability and transparency problems. On the other hand, high concern over some safety risks (e.g., chemicals or pesticide residues) may be exaggerated, suggesting some misconceptions about certain risks and hazards.

Besides the factors already mentioned, constrained actors' cooperation capacities also relate to in-house capacity in relation to appropriate cooperation tools, differences in education and training, and most notably, the contextual differences among Member States such as shared interests which, together with the resource problem may hamper effective cross-collaboration efforts.

5.2 Recommendations

The recommendations presented in this section are derived from the insights gathered during the workshops, focusing on participants' interpretation of terms such as "effective communication" and "effective engagement" in the context of food safety.

Building upon the barriers discussed in the previous section, these recommendations provide valuable insights into the specific areas and contexts where engagement gaps and needs exist. In addition, participants identified certain overarching characteristics of effective communication practices, such as simplicity, clarity, reliability, emotiveness, and truthfulness. Similarly, the nature of engagement was described as

collaborative, involving multiple actors and disciplines, and characterized by transparency.

These insights can serve as a foundation for exploring innovative approaches to public engagement, particularly in areas where progress has been impeded. By leveraging the two methods discussed, new avenues for public engagement can be explored, offering potential solutions to address the challenges faced in these areas.

Figure 2: word cloud representing the features that participants in the workshop in Portugal found relevant for effective communication.

Recommendation 1: Innovative engagement methods should be implemented to enhance food safety awareness in areas with limited literacy levels.

Though this statement holds true, especially for food safety authorities and policymakers, this recommendation goes for all food actors involved in communicating about food risks. **The vast number of topics covered points towards a need not only for more engagement approaches, but more innovative and creative ways of interacting with the public that stimulates their involvement in the agenda-setting of research and policy questions, and implementation.** The co-creation workshop approach developed a new way of engaging with diverse actors that naturally promotes co-learning and co-deliberation.

The co-creation workshop has the following features to facilitate the co-learning and co-development of communication materials through multi-actor engagement:

- **Diverse Participation:** The workshop brings together actors from various backgrounds and expertise, ensuring a broad range of opinions and perspectives are considered and respected.
- **Idea Generation:** It provides a platform for generating new ideas that can be further developed for future communication efforts and to inform research and policy initiatives.
- **Engaged Participation:** To foster active involvement in the agenda-setting process, the workshop limits the number of participants, ensuring a high level of engagement from all involved.
- **Tangible Outputs:** The workshop emphasizes the creation of tangible outputs, which can serve as valuable resources for actors interested in exploring societal knowledge gaps and addressing information needs.
- **Collaboration and Consensus:** By working towards a shared goal, the co-creation activities encourage collaboration among stakeholders with differing interests or viewpoints, facilitating consensus-building.

By incorporating these elements, **the co-creation workshop fosters an inclusive and dynamic environment for participants to collaborate, exchange knowledge, and collectively develop effective communication materials.** Additionally, the inclusion of case studies allows for discussions from various perspectives, as evidenced by the novel food campaigns presented in Table 5. This approach enhances the practicality and comprehensibility of the final outcomes.

During the Finnish workshop, three comprehensive engagement campaigns were devised to promote consumer trust in the safety of novel proteins. Each campaign offers a distinct perspective, showcasing the versatility and diversity of approaches in addressing the same issue while considering specific target groups. These campaign plans can serve as a blueprint to guide authorities, policymakers, and researchers in formulating their own public engagement strategies or campaigns aimed at building trust in novel proteins and foods, which may encounter similar barriers to acceptance.

Table 5 demonstrating the four campaigns developed in the working groups of the Finnish workshop on alternative proteins aiming to improve consumer trust around the safety of novel foods.

<p>Theme 1: Good for you, good for nature Working group 1</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The idea of the campaign is to increase consumer acceptance of alternative proteins. In Finland consumers already trust the safety of alternative proteins so the objective of this campaign is to increase the attractiveness of the new alternative proteins. • The message of the campaign is <i>“Good for you, good for nature”</i>. • Target group: teenagers and young adults. • Prime channel: social media (TikTok). • Engagement approach: in the campaign popular young influencers try new alternative proteins, describe the flavor, and create new recipes. There is also recipe competition with the followers. In the TikTok videos also the environmental aspect of eating choices and sustainable eating habits are tackled.
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<p>Theme 2: Safe food for everyone Working group 2</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The idea of the campaign is to move away from the confrontation that is the food meat or is the food vegetarian, the main point is to have safe food for everyone. • Target group: young people, adults and seniors • Idea is to make videos for different platforms: in the videos the whole production chain is shown from the fields and factories to the consumer’s table (from farm to fork). Point is to increase openness and traceability. Show the delicious foods and create new recipes with them – case examples. • Not to target just one product but industry and operators working together to produce the videos for the campaign from different new protein products. With co-operation strengthen trust and create value for new proteins.
<p>Theme 3: Science-based messages Miro group (online)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The idea of the campaign is to create science-based messages and provide information for the audience about new protein sources. • Target group: broad – targeted messages for different groups on different channels and tools. • Co-operation of the whole chain and targeted messages simultaneously. • Videos for some, podcasts and radio programmes where experts (researchers, authorities, industry) are discussing about the topic. • Also some ideas how to attract new users: stamp to the products: “Examined safety” or some other similar type slogan. Telling about safety of alternative proteins. Campaigns to attract new users to try new products.

As one approach, stakeholders can utilize the following steps to engage actors in the co-development of communication materials:

1. **Group Formation:**
 - Divide participants into smaller groups, ensuring diversity.
2. **Familiarize with Actor Profile:**
 - Review attached actor profiles based on real-life examples.
3. **Identify Communication Challenge:**
 - Discuss and reach a consensus on the primary communication challenge related to food safety and alternative proteins within your group.
4. **Determine Target Audience:**
 - Define the main target audience for your campaign based on the identified food safety issue.
 - Consider audience characteristics, needs, and concerns.
5. **Craft the Message:**
 - Develop a clear, concise, informative, and persuasive message that aligns with the communication challenge and resonates with the target audience.
6. **Design Campaign Materials:**
 - Brainstorm and create campaign materials (posters, brochures, videos, etc.) that effectively convey the message.
 - Consider the preferences and habits of the target audience.
7. **Select Communication Channels:**
 - Determine the primary channels for delivering campaign materials.
 - Consider the assigned actor's role and influence in selecting suitable channels.
 - Explore traditional and digital channels (social media, websites, press releases, collaborations).

8. Utilize the Guiding Template:

- Use the provided template to structure and develop the campaign proposal.

9. Utilize Miro Boards:

- Utilize Miro boards for group brainstorming and collaboration.

10. Present and Evaluate:

- Prepare a 5-minute presentation of the campaign proposal, including target audience, message, materials, and channels.
- Highlight the strengths and effectiveness of the communication strategy.
- Provide feedback on other groups' proposals.

In cases where there may be a need for more understanding of societal information gaps and needs regarding food safety, the public event format (Table 2) may be an effective tool for reaching wide audiences, including citizens. The public event format offers the following characteristics that can be utilized by actors in the initial stages of aiming to map out or gain a better understanding of societal views and concerns regarding food safety, and to monitor awareness gaps:

- **Inclusive Participation:** The format facilitates the participation of diverse actors with different expertise and backgrounds, ensuring a wide range of opinions are represented and highlighted in the discussions.
- **Engagement of the Public:** By involving the public in the discussions, the format provides an opportunity for their opinions to be heard and considered alongside the insights of experts.
- **Broad Societal Perspective:** The format encourages a high attendance rate, allowing for a comprehensive societal perspective on food safety issues to be captured and considered.
- **Utilization of Interactive Tools:** Tools such as Slido or Mentimeter can be employed to collect results and insights from the event, enabling the follow-up analysis and utilization of the obtained data.
- **Informative and Actionable:** The public event format is well-suited for informing recommendations, identifying areas that warrant further investigation, and facilitating the exchange of knowledge and insights.

By leveraging these characteristics, actors can create impactful public events that foster dialogue, enable knowledge sharing, and contribute to a better understanding of societal perspectives on food safety.

Both approaches can be effectively utilised in tandem: as one approach, the public event methodology can be utilized to survey and identify societal concerns during the initial stages, while the co-creation workshop offers the advantage of engaging actors in a focused manner, specifically addressing a particular food safety issue and involving them in the collaborative development of communication materials or other tangible outputs.

Additionally, **FoodSafety4EU has developed five additional public engagement tools that can be utilized in various contexts.** These tools were developed in collaboration with stakeholders in some cases, while in others, they were created by partners with interdisciplinary expertise. The value of these already tested tools lies in their ability to be easily adopted and reused by stakeholders across different contexts for public engagement.

The following are the **five tools developed or tested by FS4EU** in different contexts (further details can be found in Annex 3):

- FS4EU Communication Kit
- TikTok videos as a form of "edutainment" (combining education and entertainment)

- Comics as a form of "edutainment" (combining education and entertainment)
- Educational materials to support food safety teaching
- FSOLab Methodology Guidebook

A comprehensive description and explanation of these tools can be found in other documents and publications arising from the FoodSafety4EU project. However, a brief overview of these tools is provided in Annex 3, which includes explanations, target audiences, recommendations for reuse, and information on where to access them.

Recommendation 2: Innovative approaches to public engagement should be employed to foster cross-collaboration at all levels, particularly during outbreaks, in order to promote effective communication and coordination.

The crisis communication context emphasizes the responsibility of actors to promptly inform the relevant authority. In subsequent stages, other food actors must ensure that they communicate information from trusted sources, such as the authority, to prevent the spread of false information, which can undermine trust-building efforts. **During outbreaks or crises, the flaws and vulnerabilities in the current EU food safety system become apparent**, with varying levels of communication and engagement capacities among actors. **Discrepancies may arise due to limited resources, inadequate training capacity, and insufficient education, among other reasons** (refer to section 5.1 on "barriers"). These deficiencies hinder the promotion of food literacy. Therefore, **it is essential to promote food safety literacy not only among consumers but at all levels, with a focus on creating awareness about reliable information sources for communicating food risks, which requires collective agreement.**

Discussions revealed a lack of clarity among actors regarding who should be considered a reliable source of information during food risk situations. Participants emphasized the need to establish a collective consensus on what constitutes the "ultimate trusted source" of information, particularly during a food crisis. The salmonella incident in Belgium highlighted that journalist, facing tight deadlines, may propagate false information when all actors are not effectively cooperating or providing timely information, prioritizing efficiency over information quality. Therefore, **there is a continued need to enhance the capacity of stakeholders involved in the early communication phases of a crisis or contentious issues to ensure consistent, accurate, and harmonized external information. The innovative co-creation format, with its characteristics, is particularly relevant for communication and engagement in outbreak contexts.** It facilitates mutual learning and co-deliberation, which are crucial for developing information source literacy among actors involved in risk communication stages.

During the Belgian workshop, participants discussed various ways in which relevant actors could enhance effective cooperation and communication during a food outbreak. The table below (Table 6) captures some actor-specific recommendations.

Table 6 highlighting actor specific communication and engagement approaches enabling them to effectively address challenges linked to crisis communication.

Actor	Main challenge identified	Target group	Approach/message	Materials and channels
Food company	Transparency and timeliness of communication	Consumers & RAS	Clear and timely communication to consumers but with empathy	Social media, tv, radio, newspapers

Actor	Main challenge identified	Target group	Approach/message	Materials and channels
Policymaker	Time-lag between measuring and public action taken	Food companies	Stricter regulations that ensure information travels to the food authority and communication about the concrete steps	RASFF like portal but confidential
Food authority	Contamination of drug residues in production of milk	Companies & consumers	1 st information travels to agency about the contamination incident 2 nd agency informs client for a withdrawal. 3 rd product recall is needed when the consumer has bought product.	Public event in which company can explain the incident in clear and simple terms to the general public. Briefing to the regulatory authorities or a formal letter which includes a prevention strategy. Social media engagement e.g. via the company page Press, TV, radio which acts as a mediator
Research institute	Clear communication to make complex information digestible	General public	Clearly explaining the risks and group most likely to be affected with a focus on educating rather than blaming the responsible.	A range of channels: news, tv and papers, social media, university websites (with a focus on highlighting ongoing research surrounding the topic).

6 Conclusion

The co-creation methodology, as outlined in Table 1 and Table 2, exhibits promising features that can enhance the innovative and creative potential of stakeholders, enabling their direct contribution to the

development of new outputs that inform science and innovation processes. These outputs can take various forms based on the specific participation objectives and information needs, and lead to diverse output e.g. engagement plans, campaigns, or guidelines.

The engagement format fosters a mutual learning environment characterized by high levels of engagement, co-deliberation, and co-learning, which are conducive to comprehending and addressing complex scientific issues. The detailed stakeholder engagement plans generated by participants in the two workshops can be translated into a set of recommendations to inform policy and research outcomes (refer to Table 5 & 6). This suggests that the co-creation approach allows for in-depth information and the co-development of knowledge by small groups (6-8) of engaged actors, contrasting with the more traditional public event format, which is more effective at reaching broader audiences and raising general awareness about food safety.

Observations indicate highest motivation levels among participants in working groups when tasked with delivering outputs compared to public events, where dialogue tends to be limited to panel discussions. However, inputs collected through apps like Mentimeter and Slido, while useful in gathering a large volume of information, may be less easily translated into a set of recommendations due to their lack of coherence and issue-specific focus. Nevertheless, this format can help identify signals from society that can catalyze further investigation and topics for co-creation.

The issue-specific case-study approach, integral to the co-creation workshops, enables in-depth and detailed examination of specific cases within real-world contexts. This empowers audiences, regardless of their literacy levels, to possess sufficient contextual information to actively participate in mutual learning and co-development activities. The involvement of knowledgeable experts who share their experiences in dealing with the particular issues at hand, such as crisis communications or the development of novel proteins, fosters opportunities for direct engagement with participants, mutual growth, and the establishment of empathy and trust.

As a next step, **FS4EU recommends further research and experimentation with the co-creation workshop methodology in diverse contexts** to validate its effectiveness as a tool for involving diverse stakeholders in the co-creation and co-development of new knowledge to inform research and innovation processes. Additional testing of the format in various contexts can help address topics characterized by high levels of complexity, abstraction, and uncertainty. Moreover, further research can determine whether the two suggested formats can be successfully implemented in tandem, both in online settings and offline, and, for the co-creation workshop, further research can determine whether it can be expanded to accommodate environments with a large number of participants while maintaining the same quality of engagement – increased participation levels would be beneficial for significantly expanding the pool of ideas and outputs from which policymakers and authorities can draw inspiration.

As mentioned, **the FS4EU project has delved into a variety of tools that can be used for public engagement.** Annex 3 provides a detailed summary of **five additional tested tools that are designed for specific stakeholders, offering great potential for engaging the public effectively in diverse contexts.** Going forward, there is a strong commitment to making the recommendations and tools outlined in this document easily accessible to stakeholders in user-friendly formats such as policy briefs and factsheets. This approach aims to encourage uptake and reuse of the tools. Furthermore, the FoodSafety4EU knowledge hub will serve as a platform for making these resources available in the future.

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7 ANNEX 1 – Agendas (workshops)

EU Green Week - Partner Event

How can we communicate food safety in the context of sustainable food systems?

Online, Wednesday, 1 June 2022 - 10.00-12.00 CET

EU GREEN DEAL
MAKE IT REAL
PARTNER EVENT
#EUGREENWEEK
30 MAY - 5 JUNE 2022

How can we communicate food safety in the context of sustainable food systems?

1st June 2022

Online event | free participation

NEXT GEN EU

FoodSafety4EU
 MULTI-STAKEHOLDER PLATFORM FOR FOOD SAFETY IN EUROPE

Organisation	FoodSafety4EU (FS4EU) project
Main FoodSafety4EU challenge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensuring continued researchers-citizen-policymaker interaction and citizen contribution to the European Food Safety System (FSS).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensuring that communication toolkits, tools and methodologies are fit-for-purpose for engaging citizens and stakeholders in debates on food safety.
<p>Collaboration</p>	<p>FoodSafety4EU & EU Green Week</p>
<p>Expected outcomes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Novel insights into how continued researchers-citizen-policymaker interaction and citizen contribution to the European FSS can be achieved and ensured in the future. Stakeholder and citizen contribution to the: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of best practices ensuring continued public-researcher-policymaker interaction. Development of user-friendly toolkits, communication tools and methodologies targeted to different actors and tailored to address citizen needs/expectations.
<p>Target participants</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consumer associations General public Policymakers NGOs Food scientists All other interested stakeholders across Europe and the globe.
<p>Objectives</p>	<p>EU policy agenda, particularly the From Farm to Fork Strategy under the EU Green Deal, has placed significant importance on the transition towards more sustainable food systems and healthy diets, while maintaining a steady, high level of food safety - particularly, in the context of novel foods/methods being introduced into the food chain, that may present new, hard to assess, emerging risks. We know that science has a key role to play in this transition, but how can we guarantee that science is understood by consumers?</p> <p>The objective of the session is to have FoodSafety4EU partners and other selected speakers from the European Food Safety System showcase and reflect on their best public communication/engagement practices. Stakeholders will then identify, where relevant, existing shortcomings to be addressed.</p> <p>The introductory session would then foster debate among diverse actors/stakeholders present at the event (who will be encouraged to participate via a smartphone), that will provide novel insights into how to ensure relevant, continued public-research dialogue and collaboration, as well as citizen engagement and contribution to the European FSS in the future.</p> <p>The workshop aims to:</p> <p>Involve citizens and diverse stakeholders in discussions on best communication practices, in order to collect insights that would help ensure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relevant, continued public-researcher-policymaker interaction and sustained citizen contribution to the future European FSS. The development of tailored, innovative, user-friendly, communication tools and methodologies, targeted to different specific actors.
<p>Registration link</p>	<p>Participation is free but you need to register here.</p>

<p>Introduction 10.00 - 10.20</p>	<p>Introductory presentation</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>EUFIC will give a short introductory presentation, outlining the key objectives and structure of the session, as well as highlighting the relevant themes it will aim to address. The topic of the session, “how can we communicate food safety in the context of sustainable food systems?” will be highlighted and contextualised within the frame of the EU Green Deal and other relevant policy initiatives.</i>
<p>10.20 – 11.45</p>	<p>Interactive panel debate with experts followed by a public discussion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The goal of this session is to encourage an interactive debate among the panelists on best practices for communication and public engagement, through a mixture of short presentations given by experts, followed by a moderated Q&A, which will pave the way for a discussion with the wider public. The audience will be invited to engage in an active dialogue via the use of a smartphone through online tools e.g., Slido/Mentimeter.</i> <p>Moderators: Maria Scherbov and Matteo Sabini (EUFIC)</p> <p>Panel experts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Veronica Lattanzio – FoodSafety4EU Coordinator, CNR-ISPA • Domagoj Vrbos – Team Leader, Strategic Communications, EFSA • Dr. Suzan Fiack – Head of Unit Press and Public Relations, German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment, BfR • Barbara Tiozzo - Communication Expert Network of EFSA, Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale delle Venezie • Federica Dolce – SAFE, EU Policy Manager
<p>11.50 - 12.00</p>	<p>Wrap-up and main conclusions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maria Scherbov and Matteo Sabini – EUFIC • Karl Presser – PREMOTEC, FS4EU expert finder app

Eastern Hub workshop - the SafeConsume International Conference

Session 8: food safety in the future

Bucharest, 27-28 June 2022

Time	Session/ Activities
13:30-13:40	Welcome & Introduction and icebreaking activity
13:40-15:25	<p>8.1 Panel Debate led by Lars Mønter (Danish Council for Better Hygiene)</p> <p>Panel discussion: Maria Scherbov (EUFIC), Domagoj Vrbos (EFSA), Corina Zugravu (National Institute of Public Health, Romania), Noémie Levy (OECD)</p> <p>8.2 Interactive session</p>
15:25-15:30	Conclusion/wrap-up

Southern Hub - workshop

Do we really know what is communication effectiveness?

Date: 11 november 2022, 10.30-12.30 CET (online)

The poster features a central text area on a light beige background. To the right, there is a graphic of overlapping colorful circles in shades of pink, purple, blue, and yellow. Various icons are scattered around and on these circles, including a warning sign, a carrot, a gear, a fork and knife, and hands. The text is as follows:

WORKSHOP

Do we really know what is communication effectiveness?

11 NOVEMBER 2022

Online event | 10.30-12.30 CET

At the bottom of the poster, there is a row of logos and icons: the Food Safety 4EU logo, the website www.foodsafety4.eu, social media icons for Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram, and YouTube, and the European Union flag.

Agenda

Time	Session/ Activities
10:30 – 10:35	Welcome & Introduction and icebreaking activity
10:35 – 10:55	<i>Risk Communication responses to societal concerns in the food safety area: examples relate d to emerging risks and Transparency of Risk Assessment</i> Anthony Smith, EFSA
10:55 – 11:15	<i>What does effective communication really mean?</i> Prof. Jose Palma D’Oliveira, ASAE’s Scientific Council, Universidade de Lisboa
11:15 – 12:15	<i>Do we really know what is communication effectiveness?</i> Moderator: Prof. Rui Gaspar, President of Society for Risk Analysis Europe Panellists ASAE – Filipa Melo de Vasconcelos DGC – Ana Catarina Fonseca FIPA – Pedro Queiroz ONRE – Prof. Maria do Céu Costa
12:15 – 12:30	<i>Risk Communication funding opportunities</i> Maria Maia, FCT- Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia/ Foundation for Science and Technology
12:30 – 12:45	Conclusion/wrap-up

Northern Hub – workshop:

Food safety and consumer trust: a thematic workshop on alternative proteins

Co-creating methodologies and tools for improving communication on food safety

Luottaako kuluttaja uusien elintarvikkeiden turvallisuuteen?

Espoo, VTT MIKES (Tekniikantie 1, Aari meeting room)

Wednesday 30 November 2022 - 10.00-13.00 CET

TYÖPAJA

Luottaako kuluttaja uusien elintarvikkeiden turvallisuuteen?

Tervetuloa keskustelemaan ja ideoimaan FoodSafety4EU ja NextGenProteins projektien järjestämään tilaisuuteen

30.11.2022 klo 09:00-12:00

VTT Teknologian tutkimuskeskus, Otaniemi, Espoo

Food
Safety
4EU

www.foodsafety4.eu

<p>Organisation</p>	<p>FoodSafety4EU (FS4EU) project</p>
<p>Main FoodSafety4EU challenge</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring continued researchers-citizen-policymaker interaction and citizen contribution to the European Food Safety System (FSS). • Ensuring that communication toolkits, tools and methodologies are fit-for-purpose for engaging citizens and stakeholders, with a particular focus on young generation, in debates on food safety.
<p>Collaboration</p>	<p>FoodSafety4EU & NEXTGENProteins project</p>
<p>Expected outcomes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder and citizen contribution to the: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Development of user-friendly toolkits, communication tools and methodologies targeted to different actors and tailored to address citizen needs/expectations ○ Development of best practices ensuring continued public-researcher-policymaker interaction. • Novel insights into how continued researchers-citizen-policymaker interaction and citizen contribution to the European FSS can be achieved and ensured in the future.
<p>Target participants</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Young students and researchers • Researchers • Food Safety Authorities • Consumer associations • Policymakers • NGOs • All other interested stakeholders in the FSS
<p>Objectives</p>	<p>EU policy agenda, particularly the Farm to Fork Strategy under the EU Green Deal, has placed significant importance on the transition towards more sustainable food systems and healthy diets, while maintaining a steady, high level of food safety - particularly in the context of novel foods and methods being introduced into the food chain that may present new, hard to assess, emerging risks.</p> <p>Meanwhile, in Europe, a shift in preferences towards sustainable consumption practices has created a new interest and demand for alternative proteins (i.e. plant-based and food-technology alternatives to animal protein).</p> <p>We know that science has a key role to play in this shift and transition, but <i>how</i> can we guarantee that science is being listened to and understood by consumers?</p> <p>The objective of the workshop is to have students interact with researchers, with involvement of other actors from the European Food Safety System, to co-create a proposal/roadmap for how the public can be engaged in the European food safety system. The workshop will focus on the case of alternative proteins.</p> <p>The workshop will have two main parts:</p> <p>The first session featuring a keynote talk, an introductory presentation on communication practices, and a panel discussion with diverse food actors, will outline <u>the framework and foster debate with participants about the state of the art and best engagement practices within the realm of food safety</u> using the example of alternative proteins. The session will provide novel insights into the strengths and shortcomings of current tools/techniques, and how relevant and continued public-researcher-policymakers dialogue could be ensured in the future.</p> <p>The second part will be a co-creation workshop in which participants will be asked to work in groups to <u>design and propose an appropriate strategy to address the</u></p>

communication/engagement gaps and current barriers hindering effective engagement among specific actors with the public. These will be presented in the third session.

Thus, participants will be directly involved in the development of new tools and methodologies that would allow for the sustained engagement between public-researchers-policymakers.

The proposals could demonstrate a 'best practice' and be utilised and further publicised within the scope of the FS4EU project e.g in the context of the 2023 Forum.

The workshop aims to:

- 1) Involve workshop participants (diverse food system actors i.e. students, researchers, policymakers, authorities, consumer organisations etc.) in a debate on alternative proteins and how their safety aspects can be communicated by relevant food actors, including the tools & channels, to provide insights into current gaps/challenges of engaging with citizens.
- 2) Involve students/participants in the development of a proposals/strategy to address the gaps identified in the first session, and which will aim to improve overall public engagement practices (taking into account specific actors) in the area of alternative proteins (with a focus on communicating about their safety aspects).

Registration link

Participation is free but you need to register here. <https://www.lyyti.fi/reg/FS4EU>

<p>Welcome 10.00-10.10</p>	<p><i>Introduction and scope of the day</i></p> <p>Hanna-Leena Alakomi – VTT, FoodSafety4EU</p> <p><i>Short presentation on the FoodSafety4EU project and on the scope of the day, including the presentation of the agenda and the guidelines for participating both onsite and online. Eurobarometer – Finnish results</i></p>
<p>Keynote speeches</p> <p>10.10 - 10.30</p> <p>10.30-10.50</p>	<p><i>Communicating the safety of alternative proteins</i></p> <p>Jussi Peusa, Ylitarkastaja, Elintarvikehygienijaosto, Finnish Food Authority, <i>Introduction to food safety communication to consumers, case examples</i></p> <p>Jaakko Paasi – VTT, NEXTGENProteins</p> <p><i>This presentation will provide an overview of the NEXTGENPROTEINS survey where perceptions of 6600 European consumers in 7 different countries on new protein sources and their application in food were investigated, stimulating the following discussion and providing insights for the co-creation session.</i></p>
<p>Panel discussion 10.50 - 11.40</p>	<p><i>How to improve the communication/public engagement around alternative proteins? – as seen from different perspectives</i></p> <p>Moderators: Anu Seisto, VTT</p> <p>Panel experts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anni-Mari Syväniemi, Ruokatieto yhdistys ry, Developing arctic food culture Ruokatieto Yhdistys • Jaakko Korpela - EntoCube Oy EntoCube – EntoCube – cricket farming technology • Jussi Peusa – Finnish Food Authority • Jaakko Paasi – VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland, NextGenProteins <p><i>During this session, experts will enrich the discussion bringing their different perspective and providing elements to stimulate the following co-creative session. Each speaker will start sharing its perspective and then it will be asked to reply to the questions of the moderator. In the meantime, the onsite and online audience can share their questions to the panelists.</i></p> <p>Q&A session 10 min - Mentimeter -</p>
<p>11.40-11.50</p>	<p><i>Short break</i></p>
<p>Co-creation session 11.50- 12.30</p>	<p><i>Co-creating new tools and methodologies to improve the food safety communication on alternative proteins</i></p>

	<p><i>The audience will be divided in groups, each group will work on an assigned template to develop new tools, methodologies and messages to improve the communication on food safety. Assisted by a tutor from the FoodSafety4EU project, each group will select target, scope, content and means of communication.</i></p>
<p>Presentation & discussion 12.30 - 12.50</p>	<p><i>Presenting and discussing the co-created tools and methodologies</i></p> <p><i>A representative of each group will present the tools and the methodology created to the other participants (including the ones online). In the meantime, questions from the audience will be collected and addressed.</i></p>
<p>12.50 - 13.00</p>	<p><i>Wrap-up and main conclusions</i></p> <p>Hanna-Leena Alakomi – VTT, FoodSafety4EU</p> <p><i>The main outcome emerging from the discussion and the co-creation session will be summarised. Moreover, the initiative “Next Generation of Food Safety communicators” will be officially launched.</i></p>

Western Hub - workshop

How can we communicate food safety in the context of false information?

Co-creating methodologies and tools for improving communication on food safety

14 December 2022

16.00-18.00 CET

University of Ghent, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences

WORKSHOP hosted by UGENT

The “Salmonella” in chocolate crisis: what can we learn about effective food safety communication?

Co-design and pitch your ideas to experts to improve the risk communication!

14 DECEMBER 2022 h. 16.00-18.00 CET

Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences - Ghent University

www.foodsafety4.eu

Organisation

FoodSafety4EU (FS4EU) project

Main FoodSafety4EU challenge

- Ensuring continued researchers-citizen-policymaker interaction and citizen contribution to the European Food Safety System (FSS).
- Ensuring that communication toolkits, tools and methodologies are fit-for-purpose for engaging citizens and stakeholders in debates on food safety.

<p>Expected outcomes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Novel insights into how continued researchers-citizen-policymaker interaction and citizen contribution to the European FSS can be achieved and ensured in the future. • Stakeholder and citizen contribution to the: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Development of best practices ensuring continued public-researcher-policymaker interaction. ○ Development of user-friendly toolkits, communication tools and methodologies targeted to different actors and tailored to address citizen needs/expectations.
<p>Target participants</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consumer associations • General public • Policymakers • NGOs • Food scientists • All other interested stakeholders across Europe and the globe.
<p>Objectives</p>	<p>EU policy agenda has placed significant importance on the transition towards more sustainable food systems and healthy diets, while maintaining a steady, high level of food safety - particularly, in the context of novel foods/methods being introduced into the food chain, that may present new, hard to assess, emerging risks. Meanwhile there is wide-spread acknowledgement and concern about the propagation of unreliable or unverified information related to food safety, and its ability to influence public opinion and people’s choices when it comes to food. We know that science has a key role to play in tackling the spread of false information, but <i>how</i> can we guarantee that emerging issues are effectively being communicated to citizens and consumers to cut through the noise? Part of the ambition of the FS4EU project is to improve methods and tools for communicating and engaging with the wider public, as well as improving the understanding of how emerging issues can be communicated to citizens and consumer.</p> <p>To this end, this workshop will enable and citizen contribution to the future European Food Safety System (FSS). Active ‘dialogue between the invited participants will provide input in support of new methodologies and toolkits that will guide Food Safety Authorities, policy makers and researchers to better communicate with the large public on food safety, in turn strengthening the citizen-science-policy long-term collaboration.</p> <p>The workshop aims to:</p> <p>Involve citizens and diverse stakeholders in discussions on best practice, to collect insights that would help ensure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Relevant, continued public-researcher-policymaker interaction. ○ Citizens’ sustained contribution to the future European FSS. ○ The development of tailored, innovative, user-friendly, communication tools and methodologies, targeted to different specific actors.

16.00-16.10	Introduction: (Celine Meerpoel, FS4EU/UGent)
	<p>Aim: to present:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Scope of the FS4EU project ○ Topic of false information linked to the chocolate and salmonella scandal in Belgium ○ Workshop aims ○ Opportunities for winning team.
16.10-16.35	<p>Presentation by 3 communication experts:</p> <p>Aim of the presentation: to share diverse experiences of the chocolate and <i>Salmonella</i> case in Belgium, which will answer (and trigger) questions relevant from a communication perspective and shed light on best practices/risks/challenges for crisis communication.</p> <p>Experts confirmed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Jeroen Wils (expert in reputation and crisis communication) - Helene Bonte (spokesperson Federal Agency for the Safety of the Food Chain) - Stefan Van Rompaey (Chief editor RetailDetail, Author)
16.35-17.55 16.40-17.40 17.40- 17.55	<p>Co-creation exercise with students of UGent and presentations</p> <p>Aim: using the insights from the presentations (and focusing on different perspectives) the students will contribute their recommendations as to how crisis communication could be improved and the propagation of false information avoided; The session is guided by the speakers and designed in cooperation with Julie Clement (Strategic advisor in communication at Federal Public Service Social Security / Lector & practical assistant communication Artevelde Hogeschool & UGent</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity will be presented. 4-5 groups (of 6 students) will work together to develop a proposal that will offer recommendations for crisis communication related to the learnings from the scandal. Templates will be provided by FS4EU, with some guiding questions. • The proposals will be shared and voted on in the plenary (peer2peer), where one group will win the opportunity to pitch their proposal to renowned experts in the FS4EU Pre-forum on 15 December (trip, lunch vouchers will be covered by Ugent).
17.55 -18.00	5 minute wrap-up (Celine Meerpoel, FS4EU/UGent)

8 ANNEX 2 – Participation statistics (workshops)

9 ANNEX 3 – FS4EU public engagement toolbox

Tool	FS4EU communication kit (glossary, international day cards, winter holiday recipes)
Target audience	<p>The communication kit for improving the public awareness will be a collection of all the educational material developed during the life of the project, especially under specific communication campaign and used for improving consumers’ awareness around the communication risk.</p> <p>The communication kit is useful for all the interested stakeholder willing to go into details of a specific theme of the food safety field or that are willing to spread the concepts of communication risk to civil society.</p> <p>The kit could be used by any actors from different sectors and background, either if they are professional or not and according to the different scope they would like to reach.</p>

Recommendations

The products developed and contained in the Communication kit take into account a double perspective that make them unique from a communication point of view:

- difficult terms and concept explained in a simple language
- understandable by civil society and a very attractive graphic design

The material produced and contained in the kit could be used in different fields related to the food safety.

First of all, the communication kit will be made available through the members of the FS4EU Platform, encouraging its use and reuse.

Moreover, all the Foodsafety4EU partners are invited to use the products of the communication kit on their channels for events/activities in the food safety sector organized by them or where they are invited as speakers.

Where can it be found?

All the materials will be collected in this specific section of the Platform. Instead of Archive it will be named Education and communication materials.

The tool	Tiktok
Target audience	<p>TikTok is mainly used by children, teenagers and adolescents below age of 24. Non-specialist audiences.</p> <p>The social media video-based phone application TikTok has grown in popularity particularly among a younger demographic attracting engagement on views and commenting on short videos as the primary type of content.^[1]</p> <p>It is a mobile app that lets users create and share very short videos (up to 60 seconds) with the help of a rich assortment of filters, effects, and a large music library.</p>
Recommendations	<p>TikTok is mainly used by children, teenagers and adolescents for creating fun, creative and engaging online videos^[1]. Nowadays also public institutions are using the platform for raising awareness about e.g. public health, education, societal and environmental issues creating informative and visually engaging videos inspiring them to learn more about these issues.</p> <p>In FS4EU project the campaign strategy chosen was that of edutainment (education and entertainment), a way of educating in an informative way without forcing learning, but in an entertaining way.</p> <p>^[1] https://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acs.jchemed.0c00511 J. Chem. Educ. 2020, 97, 3858–3866</p>
References	<p>D5.2 Report of FSOLab4: recommendations for food safety communication methods</p> <p>Manuscript (Lindner et al.) in preparation.</p> <p>https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.2903/j.efsa.2021.e190402</p>

The tool	Comics
Target audience	<p>The visual format and characters can be modified according to the target audience and hence comics can be used for broad age groups.</p> <p>Comics are a way used to express ideas with images, often combined with text or other visual information. Comics typically take the form of a sequence of panels of images. In addition, textual devices such as speech balloons and captions can indicate dialogue, narration, sound effects, or other information.</p>
Recommendations	<p>Comics can be used for rising awareness and storytelling in an engaging and funny way. Depending on the characters and script used the message can be formatted in an edutainment way – combining informative education and entertainment.</p> <p>Comics can be used for sharing science-based reliable information using funny characters/avatars.</p> <p>Comics can be used also as part of infographics for several topics and context.</p> <p>Comics can be tailored for different target groups, cultural differences taken account and translated in different languages.</p>
References	<p>D5.2 Report of FSOLab4: recommendations for food safety communication methods</p> <p>Manuscript (Lindner et al.) in preparation.</p>

The tool	<p>Educational material for teachers to support their teaching activities.</p> <p><i>Materials can include leaflets, power point presentations, demonstration materials, questionnaires to students and teachers.</i></p>
Target	<p>Students and pupils in different educational levels.</p>
Recommendations	<p>The co-creation process for preparation of the teaching materials needs to be iterative, and time needs to be reserved for the process.</p> <p>In creation of educational material national level differences in curriculum need to be taken account. The teaching material should also be ready before the semester so teachers can familiarize with the material and include it into their lessons properly with respect to the topic and scheduling.</p> <p>Created material can be translated into different languages (cultural/national differences in curriculum needs to be taken account).</p>
References	<p>D5.2 Report of FSOLab4: recommendations for food safety communication methods</p> <p>Example material from the FoodSafety4EU FSOL4 pilot available: Teacher materials with information and exercises for teachers related to the topics dealt with in the flyer, distributed to teachers with the flyer at secondary schools and used as teacher materials (incl. presentation slides).</p> <p>A dedicated campaign website was set up at FFDI and is available at: FOODSAFETY4EU (Multi-Stakeholder Platform for Food Safety in Europe) - Foodnet.</p> <p>Manuscript (Lindner et al.) in preparation.</p>
	<p>Christensen, M., & Kumar Thapa, R. (2022). The social lab as a method for experimental engagement in participatory research. <i>Journal of Responsible Innovation</i>, 1–24. https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2022.2119003</p>

The tool	FSOLab Methodology Guidebook
Target audience	This guidebook is designed to support researchers who are interested in implementing social labs, drawing inspiration from the Food Safety Operational Labs (FSOLabs) implemented as part of the project FOODSAFETY4EU. Whether you're working in food safety or any other field, this guidebook provides practical guidance based on real-life experiences
Recommendations	<p>This tool is recommended to be implemented to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Gain Insights: Benefit from first-hand experiences of a social lab process conducted in an online setting. - Practical Guidance: Find step-by-step instructions and tips to implement your own social lab. - Versatile Application: While the guidebook is based on FSOLab processes, it is applicable to various topics and fields. <p>The lab approach can be implemented in various contexts. However, to ensure a successful social lab, focus on recruiting a diverse group for the core team, representing different stakeholder groups. It is important that all participants have the time and commitment to actively participate in all workshops and throughout the entire social lab process.</p>
References	<p>Marschalek, ilse, Unterfrauner, Elisabeth, Seebacher, Lisa M. , Hofer, Margit , Handler Katharina (2023) Social labs as good practice for transdisciplinary engagement processes in research and innovation Research for All, 7: 1 DOI:https://doi.org/10.14324/RFA.07.1.04</p> <p>Marschalek, ilse, Unterfrauner, E., Handler, K., Seebacher, L. M., & Hofer, M. (2022). Social Labs in Public Engagement Processes for RRI. In: Blok, V. (eds) Putting Responsible Research and Innovation into Practice. Library of Ethics and Applied Philosophy, vol 40. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-14710-4_8</p> <p>Marschalek, ilse, Blok, V., Bernstein, M., Braun, R., Cohen, J., Hofer, M., Seebacher, L. M., Unterfrauner, E., Daimler, S., Nieminen, M., Vinther Christensen, M., & Kumar Thapa, R. (2022). The social lab as a method for experimental engagement in participatory research. <i>Journal of Responsible Innovation</i>, 1–24. https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2022.2119003</p>

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